

First record of *Simulamerelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) in Kenya (Western Indian Ocean) (Caenogastropoda: Rissoidae)

Primera cita de *Simulamerelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) en Kenia (Océano Índico Occidental) (Caenogastropoda: Rissoidae)

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ABSTRACT

The presence of the rissoid *Simulamerelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) is reported for the first time from Lamu Archipelago (Kenya) based on shells sorted out of bioclastic sand samples collected in Manda Toto Island. The type material (MFNB) also includes two non-conspecific specimens. For the stability of the species, a lectotype, is designated and figured.

RESUMEN

Se registra por primera vez la presencia del rissoido *Simulamerelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) en el archipiélago de Lamu (Kenia) a partir de conchas seleccionadas de muestras de arena bioclástica recolectadas en la isla de Manda Toto. El material tipo (MFNB) también incluye dos especímenes no coespecíficos. Por lo tanto, para garantizar la estabilidad de la especie, se designa y se figura un lectotipo.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Rissoidae, Kenya, *Simulamerelina*, new record, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Rissoidae, Kenia, *Simulamerelina*, nueva cita, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

Simulamerelina Ponder, 1985 was established as a subgenus of *Manzonia* Brusina, 1870 (see PONDER, 1985: 49), then raised to genus rank by FABER & MOOLENBEEK (2004: 60) (CRISCIONE ET AL., 2016: 13; but see also CRISCIONE & PONDER, 2011: 82). Recently, new species have been described from the Pacific Ocean (French Polynesia) (AMATI ET AL.,

2023: 856) and the Indian Ocean (Oman, Persian Gulf) (AMATI & RENDA, 2025: 66), reaching to date twenty-three known Recent species. *Simulamerelina* species live on the continental shelf, and in particular in the lower intertidal, where they are usually associated with algal facies, in the tropical Western Atlantic and the tropical Indo-West

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Table I. Measurements of shells of *Simulamereлина mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) in mm, with range and mean values: 1–5 from Kenya.

Tabla I. Medidas de conchas de *Simulamereлина mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) en mm, con rangos y valores medios: 1–5 de Kenya.

Shell	1	2	3	4	5	min-max	mean
Height	1.5	1.8	1.75	1.55	1.63	1.5-1.8	1.65
Width	0.78	0.93	0.93	0.8	0.88	0.78-0.93	0.86
Height/width ratio	1.92	1.94	1.88	1.94	1.85	1.85-1.94	1.91
Aperture height	0.58	0.7	0.68	0.6	0.65	0.58-0.7	0.64
Height/aperture height ratio	2.59	2.57	2.57	2.58	2.46	2.46-2.59	2.55
N° whorls	2.9	3.25	3.2	2.9	3.1	2.9-3.25	3.1
N° axial ribs on last whorls	16	17	17	15	16	15-17	16.2
N° spiral cords on last whorls (above aperture)	7(3)	7(3)	7(3)	7(3)	7(3)	7(3)	7(3)

Pacific. There are six additional species from Western Pacific, left in open nomenclature (AMATI ET AL., 2023: 856), and four fossil ones from the Upper Oligocene and the Lower Miocene of Aquitaine (France) (LOZOUET, 1998). Studies are underway, by the author, for a broader revision of the Rissooidea of the Kenyan waters, of which some reports have already been published (AMATI, 2024a; 2024b).

So far, only four species of *Simulamereлина* have been described from the waters of the Indian Ocean: *Simulamereлина mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880: 285, pl. 20, fig. 17; AMATI ET AL., 2023: 856), originally described from Mauritius, and more recently *S. mirbatensis* Amati & Renda, 2025, *S. omanensis* Amati & Renda, 2025, and *S. sadahensis* Amati & Renda, 2025, all from Oman.

Simulamereлина mauritiana is reported here for the first time from Kenya, based on specimens sorted out of a bioclastic sand sample collected at Manda Toto Island (Lamu Archipelago).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I examined photographs of the type material deposited in the MFNB, consisting of 10 specimens, not particularly

fresh and some broken, two of which are not conspecific with the others. Additional material (seven specimens) consists of empty shells, some of which are not particularly fresh (five intact and two broken), that were sorted from bioclastic sand samples collected with a trap box for *Marginella* species, in Manda Toto Island (Lamu Archipelago, Kenya) at approximately 2 m depth. The intact adult specimens were measured (see Table I) under a stereomicroscope, with a micrometric eyepiece (with magnification $\times 90$, $\pm 10\%$ deviation), using the method of Verduin (1982). Photographs were taken with a digital camera mounted on the stereomicroscope and digitally edited with Combine-Z (Hadley, 2006).

I have used a standardised format for the citation of specimen data in the “Type material” and the “Other material examined” sections, as described by CHESTER ET AL. (2019).

Abbreviations and acronyms

CBA: Private collection of Bruno Amati (Roma, Italy),

dd: empty shell(s),

MFNB: Museum für Naturkunde Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science (Berlin, Germany).

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960
Order LITTORINIMORPHA Golikov & Starobogatov, 1975
Superfamily RISSOOIDEA J. E. Gray, 1847
Family RISSOIDAE J. E. Gray, 184
Genus *Simulamerelina* Ponder, 1985

Simulamerelina Ponder, 1985: 49.

Type species: *Merelina corruga* Laseron, 1956: 436, 479, fig. 136 by original designation.

Simulamerelina mauritiana (E. von Martens, 1880) (Figs. 1A, B, D-I)

Rissoa (Alvania) mauritiana E. von Martens, 1880: 285, pl. 20 fig. 17.

Type material. Lectotype (here designated): MAURITIUS • 1 dd (height 1.51 mm, width 0.78 mm, Fig. 1A); unprecised locality data; MFNB.109.928a. Paralectotypes: MAURITIUS • 9 dd (7 shells of *Simulamerelina mauritiana*, Fig. 1B, and 2 non-conspicuous shells: *Simulamerelina* sp., Fig. 1C and ?*Rissoinidae* sp.); unprecised locality data; MFNB.109.928b.

Other material examined: KENYA • 7 dd (Fig. 1F-I); Lamu Archipelago, Manda Toto Island; -2.21833° S, 41.015° E; 2 m depth; 2024; in bioclastic sand; D. Pettinelli legit; CBA.

Distribution: The species is known for the Western Indian Ocean (Mauritius and Kenya) (Fig. 2).

Description: Shell (Figs 1A, B, F-I; Table I) small for the genus, height 1.5–1.8 mm, width 0.78–0.93 mm, height/width ratio 1.85–1.94, slender, pupoid and strong.

Protoconch paucispiral with twisted nucleus, of 1.3 convex whorls, height 0.30 mm, nucleus diameter 0.08 mm, first half whorl diameter 0.19 mm, maximum diameter 0.34 mm. Sculpture of 5 spiral bands of microgranules, the most prominent adapical (Fig. 1F). Protoconch-teleoconch boundary well marked.

Teleoconch of 2.9–3.25 convex whorls, suture impressed. Axial sculpture on the last whorl of 15–17 slightly prosocline ribs, of same strength as spirals and fading towards the base. Spiral sculpture of strong non-equidistant cords, 2 central on the first whorl, 3 on the second whorl and 7 on the last whorl, of which 3 above the aperture, 1 on the suture line and 3 on the base. Cords II and III starting immediately after the protoconch-teleoconch boundary; cord I, subsutural, forming shortly

after a whorl. Cord II located closer to cord I. Slightly nodulose thickenings at intersections; interspaces quadrangular. Surface covered by dense regularly distributed spiral threads. Umbilical chink absent. Aperture oval, height 0.58–0.70 mm, height/aperture height ratio 2.46–2.59, peristome duplicated, internally smooth, externally thickened by a strong moderately opisthocline varix.

Coloration uniform light brown, stranded specimens almost uniform white (bleached?).

Operculum and soft parts unknown.

Remarks: VON MARTENS (1880), described *Rissoa (Alvania) mauritiana*, only shells without soft parts, from the sands of Mauritius. PONDER (1985: 49) after having examined the type material of *Rissoa (Alvania) mauritiana*, included this species in his new taxon *Simulamerelina*, based on the shell morphology similar to that of the type species, *S. corruga* (Laseron, 1956).

No records have been reported after its description (see e.g. VIADER, 1938; JAY & DRIVAS, 1987; MULOCHAU ET AL., 2020). A wrong record, from Réunion 15 m depth, can be found in the Internet <<https://web.archive.org/web/202402>

24153214/http://vieuoceane.free.fr/mollusques/intro_frame.htm> accessed on June 05 2025) likely based on a specimen belonging to a so far undescribed *Simulamerelelina* and very similar to the non-conspicuous paralectotype of Fig. 1C (Jay *et al.*, 2009). The same holds for the specimens figured on the internet (POPPE & POPPE, 1994-2025), one of which (Fig. 1J) is the same specimen figured by JAY *ET AL.* (2009) and is not identifiable with *S. mauritiana* (probably belonging to an as yet undescribed *Simulamerelelina* and very similar to the non-conspicuous paralectotype, Fig. 1C).

One of the two non-conspicuous syntypes, now paralectotype (Fig. 1C), despite lacking the first whorls of the spire, is easily classified in the genus

Simulamerelelina, and belongs to an undescribed species. Compared to *S. mauritiana*, this specimen has a shell with an echinate sculpture and with only two spiral cords on the whorls and six on the last, two of which are above the aperture (seven of which three above the aperture in *S. mauritiana*). It has a smaller aperture, wider and more incised sutures, and fewer axial ribs on the whorls. The other non-conspicuous syntype (now paralectotype) is too broken in several places, therefore difficult to determine, but could be a species of Rissoinidae. Given the heterogeneity of the syntypes, the designation of a lectotype conforming to the original description was needed to stabilize the use of the name.

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(Right page) Figure 1. A, B, D-I: *Simulamerelelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880); C, J: *Simulamerelelina* sp. A: lectotype, Mauritius, height 1.51 mm, width 0.78 mm, MFNB.109.928a; B: paralectotype, Mauritius, height 1.50 mm, width 0.83 mm, MFNB.109.928b; C: paralectotype, Mauritius, height 1.40 mm MFNB.109.928b (Figs A-C, E ©MFNB); D: original drawing; E: original labels; F: detail of the protoconch and teleoconch microsculpture, Kenya, Lamu Archipelago, Manda Toto Island; G-I: shells, Kenya, Lamu Archipelago, Manda Toto Island, height 1.50 mm, width 0.78 mm, CBA. J. Shell, *Simulamerelelina* sp. (as *Simulamerelelina mauritiana*), Réunion (© Guido & Philippe Poppe - www.conchology.be), height 1.5 mm.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. A, B, D-I: *Simulamerelelina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880); C, J: *Simulamerelelina* sp. A: lectotipo, Mauricio, altura 1,51 mm, ancho 0,78 mm, MFNB.109.928a; B: paralectotipo, Mauricio, altura 1,50 mm, ancho 0,83 mm, MFNB.109.928b; C: paralectotipo, Mauricio, altura 1,40 mm MFNB.109.928b (Figs. A-C, E ©MFNB); D: dibujo original; E: etiquetas originales; F: detalle de la microescultura de protoconcha y teleoconcha, Kenia, archipiélago de Lamu, isla Manda Toto; G-I: conchas, Kenia, Archipiélago de Lamu, Isla Manda Toto, altura 1,50 mm, anchura 0,78 mm, CBA. J. Concha, *Simulamerelelina* sp. (como *Simulamerelelina mauritiana*), Reunión (© Guido & Philippe Poppe - www.conchology.be), altura 1,5 mm.

Figure 2. Type locality (yellow dot) of *Simulamereleina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880) Mauritius, Indian Ocean. New record (red dot) from Kenya, Lamu Archipelago, Manda Toto Island (map made with SimpleMappr (Shorthouse 2010).

Figura 2. Localidad tipo (punto amarillo) de *Simulamereleina mauritiana* (von Martens, 1880), Mauricio, Océano Índico. Nueva cita (punto rojo) de Kenia, Archipiélago de Lamu, Isla Manda Toto (mapa elaborado con SimpleMappr (SHORTHOUSE, 2010).

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